

RehabMove 2018: COMPUTATIONAL MODELING OF IMPAIRED MOVEMENTS AND RESTAURATION THERE-OF

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PURPOSE: The restauration of impaired movements requires highly individualized treatments. Therefore, it is essential to have diagnostic tools that can be used to not only demonstrate the special requirements of a patient but also to develop individualized therapies or assistive technology to restore the impairments.

Computational models can help to improve diagnoses but also to predict the outcome of possible interventions or assistive technologies.

METHODS: We have developed a so-called mixed dynamics musculoskeletal three-dimensional model. It can be used to calculate the inverse dynamics of a measured movement, i.e. the net-torques and net-forces at the joints, but also the optimized muscular activation of the complex muscular system acting at a specific joint. Based on that, we calculate the absolute forces at that joint, and by changing several properties, e.g. muscular forces, activation patterns, or assistive technologies, we predict their possible influence on specific impairments.

RESULTS: Based on selected examples, the possibilities and limits of these computational models will be presented.

CONCLUSIONS: Modern computational models will become an important tool to support people with specific impairments and to develop assistive technologies or individualized interventions.